

Appendix Table 2. Brocket deer element percentages for selected structures.

Structures selected for Tables 2-7 include those with the highest numbers of specific taxa, as well as a range of building types.

	Q-54 hall	Q-92 house	Q-95 temple	Q-97 hall	R-112	R-106
carpal		0.5%				
metapodial/phalanges	20.0%	23.0%	24.3%	32.1%	19.4%	36.7%
patella	0.4%	0.5%				
pelvis	6.5%	4.5%	2.2%	8.3%	5.6%	
rib	5.7%	12.0%	2.2%	3.6%	19.4%	3.3%
shoulder	4.8%	7.0%	2.2%	3.6%	2.8%	3.3%
skull	0.4%	0.5%	0.7%			
tarsal	7.0%	7.0%	13.2%	8.3%	5.6%	16.7%
upper limb	17.8%	11.0%	16.2%	15.5%	5.6%	13.3%
upper limb lower	26.1%	15.5%	19.9%	20.2%	30.6%	23.3%
vertebra	11.3%	18.5%	18.4%	8.3%	11.1%	16.7%
limb			0.7%			